

Comparison of POD-Based Nuclide Number Density Prediction Methods for Nuclide Transmutation Calculations

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates two POD-based nuclide number density prediction methods for nuclide transmutation calculations: the Masuda method and the Urase method. Both methods were reformulated within a unified theoretical framework by introducing a small scaling factor f during the construction of the POD basis, which suppresses the contribution of nuclides excluded from the simplified chain. Singular value analyses showed that when $f \leq 10^{-25}$, the singular value spectrum converges within approximately 70 POD modes. Theoretical analysis demonstrated that the two methods are mathematically equivalent when the POD basis is constructed with the f -scaled snapshots, and numerical verification confirmed this equivalence. Without introducing f , however, a clear difference in prediction accuracy was observed. These findings clarify the relationship between the two methods and emphasize the essential role of the scaling factor f in ensuring consistent and reliable predictions.

Keywords: Fission products, Nuclide number density, Simplified chain, Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD)

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate prediction of the time-dependent variations in the number densities of fission products (FPs) is of great importance in nuclear engineering. Such predictions are essential, for example, for the safe operation of nuclear power plants and for the proper management of spent nuclear fuel.

This numerical procedure is referred to as a nuclide transmutation (burnup) calculation. While a detailed burnup chain including more than one thousand nuclides is usually adopted, it is computationally impractical for reactor core design and fuel cycle analysis. Instead, simplified chains are often employed, in which only nuclides with a dominant impact on concerned parameters are retained. However, in this approach, the number densities of nuclides excluded from the chain cannot be directly obtained.

To address this issue, methods based on the Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) have been proposed to estimate the number densities of nuclides excluded from simplified-chain results. The Masuda method [1] reconstructs the number densities by projecting the simplified-chain results onto a POD basis space constructed in advance from both detailed- and simplified-chain data. The Urase method [2], originally developed to estimate in-core power distributions from ex-core detector responses, can also be applied to nuclide transmutation calculations.

The purpose of this study is to compare the Masuda and Urase methods under identical data sets and conditions, focusing on their prediction accuracy for nuclide number densities and clarifying the theoretical relationship between the two.

2. THEORY

2.1. Conditions for Method Examination

In nuclide transmutation calculations, a *burnup chain* represents the set of nuclides and their decay/production links used to advance number densities in time. A *detailed chain*, which typically involves more than one thousand nuclides, specifies the time-dependent number density changes of all nuclides and provides highly accurate reference solutions, but requires significant computational cost. To reduce this burden, reactor core design calculations usually extract only the nuclides that significantly affect the neutron multiplication factor (reactivity), and perform number density predictions only for those nuclides. Such a reduced burnup chain is referred to as a *simplified chain*.

In the simplified chain, the effects of nuclides not explicitly considered are indirectly taken into account by rearranging the chain structure or by adjusting fission yield values. Therefore, calculations of nuclide transmutation using the simplified chain are expected to maintain sufficient accuracy. On the other hand, nuclides with only a minor impact on the target quantity (e.g., reactivity during burnup) are neglected, and thus their number densities cannot be predicted within the simplified chain framework. If one wishes to obtain the number densities of such neglected nuclides, one must instead construct another simplified chain specifically designed for that purpose, or use a detailed chain with a larger number of explicitly treated nuclides.

The relationship between the detailed and simplified chains is conceptually illustrated in Figure 1. Building on this framework, the present study focuses on reconstructing the number densities of nuclides excluded from the simplified chain by using information obtained from both the detailed and simplified chains at multiple time steps. To this end, two methods, the Masuda and Urase methods are compared under the same datasets and conditions, and their prediction accuracy is systematically evaluated.

Figure 1. Conceptual illustration of the relationship between detailed and simplified chains.

2.2. Masuda Method

The Masuda method predicts the number densities of neglected nuclides by utilizing a POD basis constructed from snapshot data obtained from both the detailed chain and the simplified chain. Let $\mathbf{y}_L^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_L}$ denote the number density vector of nuclides included in the simplified chain at time step t , and let $\mathbf{y}_H^{(t)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_H}$ denote that of nuclides excluded from the simplified chain. Let N be the number of snapshot time steps used for POD basis construction. By arranging these vectors at multiple time steps side-by-side, the snapshot matrix \mathbf{Y} is defined as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_L^{(1)} & \mathbf{y}_L^{(2)} & \cdots & \mathbf{y}_L^{(N)} \\ f \mathbf{y}_H^{(1)} & f \mathbf{y}_H^{(2)} & \cdots & f \mathbf{y}_H^{(N)} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_L+n_H) \times N} \quad (1)$$

Here, f is a small positive scaling factor introduced to suppress the influence of the \mathbf{y}_H components during POD basis construction. Through this treatment, the contribution of excluded nuclides is reduced, and \mathbf{y}_H is treated as a quantity dependent on \mathbf{y}_L in the reduced-order representation.

Applying the singular value decomposition (SVD) to Eq. (1) yields

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{V}^T \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_L+n_H) \times (n_L+n_H)}$ is an orthonormal matrix whose column vectors \mathbf{u}_i form a POD basis, \mathbf{D} is a diagonal matrix containing the singular values in descending order, and \mathbf{V} consists of the corresponding right singular vectors.

For prediction, a composite state vector is constructed from the simplified-chain result as

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}_L \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_L+n_H)} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{y}_L \in \mathbb{R}^{n_L}$ is obtained from a simplified-chain calculation, and the zero block corresponds to the components of the excluded nuclides.

The coefficient vector in the reduced POD subspace is then obtained by orthogonal projection onto the truncated POD basis:

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{U}_J^T \hat{\mathbf{y}} \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_J = [\mathbf{u}_1 \ \mathbf{u}_2 \ \dots \ \mathbf{u}_J]$ denotes the truncated POD basis consisting of the first J modes.

Finally, the number densities of the neglected nuclides are reconstructed as

$$\mathbf{y}_H^{\text{pred}} = \frac{1}{f} \mathbf{U}_{H,J} \mathbf{x} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{U}_{H,J}$ represents the rows of \mathbf{U}_J corresponding to the excluded nuclide components. In this manner, the Masuda method reconstructs the number densities of excluded nuclides as quantities dependent on \mathbf{y}_L , while maintaining numerical stability and subspace consistency through the introduction of the scaling factor f .

2.3. Urase Method

The Urase method predicts unobserved components from observable quantities by solving an inverse problem in the POD space using a pseudoinverse. The same snapshot matrix \mathbf{Y} defined in the previous subsection is used for POD basis construction.

Applying SVD to \mathbf{Y} yields

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{V}^T \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_L+n_H) \times (n_L+n_H)}$ is the POD basis matrix constructed from the f -scaled snapshots. The matrix \mathbf{U} is partitioned as

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_L \\ \mathbf{U}_H \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{U}_L \in \mathbb{R}^{n_L \times (n_L+n_H)}, \quad \mathbf{U}_H \in \mathbb{R}^{n_H \times (n_L+n_H)} \quad (7)$$

To extract only the observable components corresponding to the simplified chain, a selection matrix is defined as

$$\mathbf{M} = [\mathbf{I}_{n_L} \quad \mathbf{0}_{n_L \times n_H}] \quad (8)$$

so that the observable vector satisfies $\mathbf{y}_L = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{y}$.

Assuming that the full state vector can be approximated within the reduced POD subspace spanned by the first J POD modes, the state is expressed as

$$\mathbf{y} \approx \mathbf{U}_J \mathbf{x}, \quad \mathbf{U}_J \in \mathbb{R}^{(n_L+n_H) \times J}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^J \quad (9)$$

Accordingly, the observable part is written as

$$\mathbf{y}_L \approx \mathbf{M}\mathbf{U}_J \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{U}_{L,J} \mathbf{x}, \quad \mathbf{U}_{L,J} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_L \times J} \quad (10)$$

For a given observation vector $\mathbf{y}_L \in \mathbb{R}^{n_L}$, the POD coefficient vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^J$ is determined as the least-squares solution of the overdetermined system $\mathbf{U}_{L,J} \mathbf{x} \approx \mathbf{y}_L$. This yields

$$\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{U}_{L,J})^\dagger \mathbf{y}_L \quad (11)$$

where $(\cdot)^\dagger$ denotes the Moore–Penrose pseudoinverse.

Finally, the number densities of the nuclides excluded from the simplified chain are reconstructed as

$$\mathbf{y}_H^{\text{pred}} = \frac{1}{f} \mathbf{U}_{H,J} \mathbf{x}, \quad \mathbf{U}_{H,J} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_H \times J} \quad (12)$$

In this manner, the Urase method estimates the POD coefficient vector from the observable components \mathbf{y}_L using a pseudoinverse-based least-squares projection, and subsequently reconstructs the excluded components \mathbf{y}_H within the reduced POD subspace.

2.4. Theoretical Equivalence of the Masuda and Urase Methods

Both the Masuda and Urase methods estimate the number densities of nuclides excluded from the simplified chain by approximating the full state vector within a reduced POD subspace constructed from the f -scaled snapshot matrix. The full state vector is approximated as

$$\mathbf{y} \approx \mathbf{U}\mathbf{x}, \quad \mathbf{U} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_L \\ \mathbf{U}_H \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{U} denotes the POD basis constructed from the snapshot matrix defined in Eq. (1), and \mathbf{U}_L and \mathbf{U}_H correspond to the components associated with the nuclides included in and excluded from the simplified chain, respectively.

Because the scaling factor f suppresses the contribution of the excluded components in the snapshot matrix, the POD basis vectors are dominated by the simplified-chain components. As a result, the submatrix \mathbf{U}_L becomes approximately orthonormal when f is sufficiently small, satisfying

$$\mathbf{U}_L^\top \mathbf{U}_L \approx \mathbf{I}, \quad \mathbf{U}_L^\dagger \approx \mathbf{U}_L^\top \quad (14)$$

This approximation becomes increasingly accurate as the scaling factor f approaches zero.

In the Masuda method, the POD coefficient vector is obtained by an orthogonal projection of the observable vector \mathbf{y}_L onto the reduced POD subspace:

$$\mathbf{x}_M = \mathbf{U}_L^T \mathbf{y}_L \quad (15)$$

In contrast, the Urase method estimates the same coefficient vector as the least-squares solution using the pseudoinverse:

$$\mathbf{x}_U = (\mathbf{U}_L)^\dagger \mathbf{y}_L \quad (16)$$

Using the approximate orthonormality of \mathbf{U}_L expressed in Eq. (14), the two coefficient vectors become identical:

$$\mathbf{x}_M \approx \mathbf{x}_U \quad (17)$$

Substituting Eqs. (15)–(17) into the reconstruction formulas of the two methods, the predicted number densities of the excluded nuclides satisfy

$$\mathbf{y}_H^{\text{pred(M)}} \approx \mathbf{y}_H^{\text{pred(U)}} \quad (18)$$

Therefore, when the POD basis is constructed using the f -scaled snapshot matrix and the scaling factor f is sufficiently small, the Masuda and Urase methods become mathematically equivalent. This equivalence explains the identical prediction accuracy observed in the numerical results when the f -scaled POD basis is employed.

3. NUMERICAL TEST

3.1. Calculation Target and Conditions

The test problem considered in this study is the time evolution of FP nuclide number density after the thermal neutron-induced pulsed fission of U-235. These data provide a suitable benchmark for verifying the accuracy of simplified-chain-based prediction methods.

Two burnup chain methods were employed: a detailed chain and a simplified chain. The detailed chain contains 1401 nuclides, covering all FPs and their decay and production paths, and thus represents a highly accurate reference calculation. These data are taken from JENDL/FPD-2011 and FPY-2011 [3]. In contrast, the simplified chain includes only 138 nuclides that have a dominant effect on the neutron multiplication factor. The influence of nuclides excluded from this chain is indirectly considered through restructuring of the burnup chain and adjustment of cumulative fission yields.

Snapshot data used for constructing the POD basis were obtained exclusively from the detailed-chain calculation at multiple time steps. The snapshot matrix therefore contains both \mathbf{y}_L and \mathbf{y}_H components extracted from the detailed chain, while the simplified-chain calculation is used only to provide \mathbf{y}_L during the prediction phase.

The snapshot matrix used for POD basis construction consists of $N = 3501$ snapshots, corresponding to all time steps of the burnup calculation. These snapshots cover the entire temporal evolution of nuclide number densities following the pulsed fission event, and are sufficient to capture the dominant temporal correlations required for constructing a representative POD basis.

The purpose of this test problem is to evaluate the capability of each method to reconstruct the number densities of nuclides excluded from the simplified chain by comparing the predictions with the reference results from the detailed chain. All calculations were conducted under identical physical and temporal conditions.

3.2. Singular Value Distribution with Respect to f

SVD was performed on the snapshot matrix constructed with different values of the scaling factor f . The distributions of singular values are summarized in Figure 2. As the absolute value of f decreases, the singular values approach almost zero with fewer basis dimensions. In particular, when f is smaller than 10^{-25} , the distribution of singular values exhibits almost no further change. For the case of $f = 10^{-25}$, the singular values converge to almost zero at approximately 70 dimensions. This indicates that the information content of the snapshot matrix is effectively governed by the simplified-chain components, and the effect of the excluded nuclides is sufficiently suppressed through the f -scaled snapshot construction.

Based on these results, the subsequent numerical predictions were carried out using $f = 10^{-25}$ and a POD basis dimension of 70.

Figure 2. Distributions of normalized singular values of snapshot matrices with different scaling factors f .

3.3. Prediction of Sn-126 Number Density

As an example, the predicted number density of Sn-126 is shown in Figure 3. It is observed that both the Masuda and Urase methods, when projected onto a 70-dimensional POD space, can reproduce the reference data with an error of less than 1%. On the other hand, when the POD basis dimension is limited to 5, the prediction accuracy significantly deteriorates, leading to oscillatory behavior in the number density.

Figure 3. Predicted number density of Sn-126 using Masuda and Urase methods with different POD basis dimensions.

3.4. Evaluation of Maximum Absolute Error for All Nuclides

To investigate the effect of introducing the factor f , the maximum absolute error of the predicted number densities was evaluated for all nuclides. Since light stable nuclides do not undergo transmutation and their number densities remain constant, they were excluded from the evaluation as prediction of such nuclides is not meaningful. The maximum error for number densities of nuclide i is defined as

$$\varepsilon_i^{\max} = \max_t \left| \hat{y}_i^{(t)} - y_i^{\text{ref}(t)} \right|, \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{y}_i^{(t)}$ is the predicted number density and $y_i^{\text{ref}(t)}$ is the corresponding reference value obtained from the detailed chain.

Figure 4 shows the distribution of the maximum absolute error for each nuclide index when the factor f is introduced. Both the Masuda and Urase methods exhibit comparable predictive accuracy, with most nuclides showing errors below 1%. This confirms that the f -scaled POD basis enables stable and accurate prediction.

Figure 4. Maximum absolute error of nuclide number density prediction (with factor f).

When the factor f is not introduced, as shown in Figure 5, the prediction errors increase in both the Masuda and Urase methods. In addition, the errors of the two methods no longer coincide, indicating that their theoretical equivalence does not hold without the f -scaled POD basis. These results highlight the essential role of the factor f in achieving both accuracy and consistency between the two methods.

Figure 5. Maximum absolute error of nuclide number density prediction (without factor f).

Figure 5 shows that when the scaling factor f is not introduced, the prediction accuracy of the Masuda and Urase methods does not necessarily coincide for all nuclides. While the differences are generally small, the Urase method appears to be slightly superior for a limited number of nuclides.

This behavior can be explained by the difference in how the two methods treat the excluded components during coefficient estimation. In the Masuda method, the excluded components are implicitly constrained to be zero in the construction of the composite vector, whereas in the Urase method they are not included in the least-squares fitting of the coefficient vector. For nuclides that are weakly correlated with the simplified-chain components, the zero-constraint assumption may introduce a small bias in the coefficient estimation, while ignoring such components can sometimes lead to a more favorable approximation.

When the scaling factor f is introduced, the contribution of the excluded components is sufficiently suppressed during POD basis construction, and the two treatments become mathematically equivalent. As a result, the prediction accuracy of the Masuda and Urase methods coincides for all nuclides, as observed in the figure.

4. CONCLUSION

This study compared two POD-based nuclide number density prediction methods for nuclide transmutation calculations: the Masuda method (orthogonal projection in a POD space) and the Urase method (pseudoinverse-based reconstruction). Both methods were reformulated under a unified framework by introducing a small positive scaling factor f to the excluded components when constructing the POD basis.

From singular value analyses, the spectrum became effectively governed by the simplified-chain components when $f \leq 10^{-25}$, saturating around a POD dimension of ~ 70 . Under this condition, both methods reproduced the reference (detailed chain) with an error of about 1% or less for representative nuclides such as Sn-126.

Theoretical analysis demonstrated that the two methods are equivalent when the POD basis is generated with the f -scaled snapshots, and the prediction results confirmed this equivalence. Without introducing f , however, the methods showed differences in accuracy, and the underlying reason remains an open topic for further study.

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